

BRANDING IN INTERNATIONAL MARKET – A RESEARCH STUDY ABOUT TIRUPUR, INDIA

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Abstract

International Marketing is in continuous uptrend, due to the digitalised platform of marketing. As technology creates leaps in communication, transportation, and financial flows, the world continues to feel smaller and smaller. It is possible for companies and consumers to conduct business in almost any country around the world thanks to advances in international trade. Tirupur is considered as an export hub, and land of garments where premium end quality brands are being manufactured and are available in product display in giant retail stores across boundaries. Entrepreneurs in Tirupur are more comfortable in dealing business in foreign labels. Very few brands of Tirupur, India are in the name of Indian brands in the global market. This study is to understand the reasons for the entrepreneurs' opinion and factors that hinders the branding and labelling of Tirupur based garments in Indian names. Primary and secondary data were collected to rule out the findings of the study. The results proves that, the success is in near future, sure "Indian garments will acquire a prominent niche under Indian brand names in the global market".

Keywords: International Marketing, Branding, Garments.

1.1 INTRODUCTION TO THE STUDY

International Marketing is in continuous uptrend, due to the digitalised platform of marketing. As technology creates leaps in communication, transportation, and financial flows, the world continues to feel smaller and smaller. It is possible for companies and consumers to conduct business in almost any country around the world thanks to advances in international trade. Brands and products that originate in one country are enthusiastically accepted in others. For example, Louis Vuitton handbags, BMWs, and Columbian coffee, all foreign products, are symbols of status and quality in the United States – and many American brands, like Warner Brothers motion pictures, have similar footholds overseas.

However, globalization has created just as many challenges as opportunities for brands that venture overseas. Because consumers have so many more options for similar products, companies must ensure that their products are high in quality and affordability. Additionally, these products cannot be marketed identically across the globe.

International marketing takes more into consideration than just language – it involves culture, market saturation, and customer behaviours. American and European companies especially have turned their international marketing efforts into something more than just exporting – they have adapted their branding to account for differences in consumers, demographics, and world markets.

Companies who have done this very well include Coca-Cola, who discovered that the word 'Diet' carries a negative connotation in Latin America and changed the name of their zero-calorie product to 'Coke Lite' for those countries. UPS, known in America for their brown trucks, issued a fleet of a different color after learning that their flagship brown trucks resembled Spanish hearses. The study is to find the significance of branding of apparel products from Tirupur for the international market.

Branding In International Market

"In an age of hyper-competition, commoditization, globalization and rapid technological obsolescence, marketers are struggling to find new conceptual bases... There are two answers to the marketing challenge facing today's companies. One is to know your customers better and get close to them. The other is to differentiate your offering through branding work so that the offering stands out as relevant and superior in value to a clear target market... Branding is much more than attaching a name to an offering.

Branding involves what people think about your business and your products. "Think of a brand as a reputation," says Paul Williams, founder of the international marketing firm Idea Sandbox, which helps companies build their brands. "Building a reputation in any new market, including overseas, involves a first impression, which comes from the initial interactions someone has with your company, products, and services."

Businesses can attempt to shape or form the branding of their company or products in many ways, including advertising, media, word-of-mouth, and contact with your products or services. A lot of thought and effort goes into branding, including naming products, designing logos, and ensuring that service is uniform throughout the business. Through continued exposure over time, your brand -- or your reputation -- is formed with potential and existing customers. "A brand is essentially a short cut, it is a way for a customer to get an instant recognition on what the promise is of a product or service and how that will benefit them," Roth says.

The reason businesses spent time and money developing brand recognition is so that they can charge a premium for a product or service. People will pay more for a brand name product or service if it is recognized as a leader and a trusted brand and they know what they will get. Apple, for example, can charge more for its computers than some other companies because of its brand reputation for offering innovative design and quality electronics. The same can be said about Mercedes or BMW automobiles. Likewise apparel brands like Versace, Gucci, Armani charge more for their quality, design and innovation.

1.2 Industry Profile Textile Industry

1.2.1 Global Market

Global textile market has been witnessing high growth over the past decade and is expected to grow at a significant rate owing to its widespread use in numerous end user industries. Textiles can be classified as natural and synthetic textile fibers. Natural fibers are sourced from animals and plants such as wool and silk whereas synthetic fibers are derived from polymers such as polyester, nylon and acrylic among others. Rapid urbanization and improving lifestyle of

consumers, particularly in emerging economies of Latin America and Asia Pacific are anticipated to be key factors for textile market. Additionally, increased use of technical textiles in industrial and medical applications is likely to be one of the key drivers for textile market. Stringent industrial regulations to use protective clothing while doing hazardous work have triggered the market for industrial textiles. Furthermore, growing fashion industry across the globe is also anticipated to augment textile market over the next six years. However, natural fibers made from animal skins such as wool and silk is expected to hamper market growth owing to stringent regulations in European region.

Textiles have a wide range of applications, the most common being clothing and in the manufacture of other household products such as carpets, bed sheets and curtains. The market for textiles can also be segmented on the basis of their specialized usage as fibers, yarns, and fabrics. Fibers can further be classified on the basis of their raw materials as cotton fibers, wool fibers, plant fibers and manmade fibers. Fabrics are derived from blending different fibers through knitting or weaving to produce various garments and industrial textiles. Fabrics are expected to be the largest application segment for textile fibers over the forecast period.

1.2.2 Indian Textile Industry

India's textiles sector is one of the oldest industries in Indian economy dating back several centuries. Our economy is largely dependent on the textile manufacturing and trade in addition to other major industries. Around 35 million people are directly employed in the textile manufacturing activities. Indirect employment including the manpower engaged in agricultural based raw- material production like cotton and related trade and handling could be stated to be around another 60 million.

The textiles industry is also labour intensive and is one of the largest employers. The textile industry has two broad segments. First, the unorganised sector consists of handloom, handicrafts and sericulture, which are operated on a small scale and through traditional tools and methods. The second is the organised sector consisting of spinning, apparel and garments segment which apply modern machinery and techniques such as economies of scale.

The Indian textiles industry is extremely varied, with the hand-spun and handwoven textiles sectors at one end of the spectrum, while the capital intensive sophisticated mills sector at the other end of the spectrum. The decentralised power looms/ hosiery and knitting sector form the largest component of the textiles sector. The close linkage of the textile industry to agriculture (for raw materials such as cotton) and the ancient culture and traditions of the country in terms of textiles make the Indian textiles sector unique in comparison to the industries of other countries. The Indian textile industry has the capacity to produce a wide variety of products suitable to different market segments, both within India and across the world.

Structure of India's Textile Industry

Unlike other major textile- producing countries, India's textile industry is comprised mostly of small-scale, non- integrated spinning, weaving, finishing and apparel- making enterprises. This unique industry structure is primarily a legacy of government policies that have promoted

labour-intensive, small- scale operations and discriminated against larger scale firms:

Composite Mills: Relatively large-scale mills that integrate spinning, weaving and sometimes, fabric finishing are common in other major textile producing countries. In India, however, these types of mills now account for about only 3 percent of output in the textile sector. About 276 composite mills are now operating in India, most owned by the public sector and many deemed financially “sick”.

Spinning: Spinning is the process of converting cotton or manmade fibre into yarn to be used for weaving and knitting. Largely due to deregulation beginning in the mid-1980s, spinning is the most consolidated and technically efficient sector in India’s textile industry. Average plant size remains small, however, and technology outdated, relative to other major producers.

Weaving and Knitting: Weaving and knitting converts cotton, manmade, or blended yarns into woven or knitted fabrics. India’s weaving and knitting sector remains highly fragmented, small-scale and labour intensive. This sector consists of about 3.9 million handlooms, 380,000 “power loom” enterprises that operate about 1.7 million looms, and just 137,000 looms in the various composite mills.

Fabric Finishing: Fabric Finishing (also referred to as processing), which includes dyeing, printing, and other cloth preparation prior to the manufacture of clothing, is also dominated by a large number of independent, small scale enterprises. Overall, about 2,300 processors are operating in India, including about 2,100 independent units and 200 units that are integrated with spinning, weaving or knitting units.

1.2.3 Tirupur Textile Industry

Tirupur is the seventh largest city in Tamilnadu and is one of the fastest developing cities in the state. Popularly referred to as “Dollar City” or “Small Japan” or “Banian City” it excels in knitted ready-made garments. Yet, at first glance, nothing about Tirupur can make one believe that this town earns an annual \$1200 million plus in foreign exchange. This is because the state government and local municipal authorities have been too slow to cope with this dynamic growth.

The main problems and difficulties faced by the Tirupur Garment industry relate to raw material availability, pricing, subsidiary and ancillary industries like processing units, labour, taxation and other law-enforcing agencies.

Tirupur is a textile District of Tamilnadu. It is one of the fastest developing Districts in Tamilnadu. Tirupur is famous for cotton knitted garment wear. It is situated near Coimbatore which is “The Manchester of South India”. It is a city in the south Indian state of Tamilnadu. It is located on the banks of the Noyyal River, which separates the city in to roughly two halves. It is the administrative headquarter of Tirupur district Tirupur’s hosiery factories are more profitable in India’s economy. Tirupur is one of the largest foreign exchange earning towns in India. Tirupur is basically a traditional centre for cotton ginning. Tirupur exports many textile items and clothing. The city accounts for 90% of India’s cotton knitwear exports to all over the world. Tirupur is a textile hub. The textile industry based at Tirupur provides employment to

over six lakh people and has an annual turnover of 220 billion Indian rupees. Of this, 120 billion rupees constitutes exports and the remaining 100 billion rupees comes from domestic sales.

International Brands

It is called the Knit Capital of India as it caters to famous brands retailers from all over the world. Nearly every international knitwear brand in the world has a strong production share from Tirupur.

It has a wide range of factories which export all types of Knits fabrics and supply garments for Kids, Ladies, and Men’s garments – innerwear exclusive. The city is known for its hosiery exports and provides employment for about 600,000 people.

Some of the world’s largest retailers including C&A , Switcher SA, Walmart , Primark , Super dry, Switcher, Polo Ralph Lauren, Diesel , ARMY , Tommy Hilfiger, M&S, FILA, Respect, H&M, HTHP, Whale, Reebok import many textiles items and clothing from Tirupur city.

1.4 Statement of the Problem

Indian Textile industry contributes 5% to India’s GDP. Exports in India is booming in a continuous manner. Producing a quality product that suits export order is a great challenge for the exporters. International fashion brands get the buyer’s attention easily when compared to domestic labels. Exporters are selling “Made in India” brands under foreign labels. This study

has a focus to understand the export market situation for apparel products in Tirupur. The main objectives are to understand the export marketers opinion and reasons for choosing foreign labels for their export goods. The study is to further describe the customers purchase choices with regard to apparel brands. The results of the study may throw light in understanding the challenges and suggestive measures will be recommended. The researcher emphasize “Brand in India” and “Brand from India” concepts to spread awareness among apparel exporters to install the thought of going for own brands for their products and to target in national and international market.

1.5 Objective of the Study

Primary Objective

- To find the exporters opportunities to “brand from India” with regard to apparel products, Tirupur.

Secondary Objective

- To understand the export market scenario of textile products in Tirupur.
- To find the factors that influences the exporters in going for foreign brands and labels.
- To study the customers opinion with regard to their purchase choice of apparel brands.
- To assess the challenges of the exporters for creating their own brands for the international market.
- To find the growth opportunities for the Tirupur exporters in going for foreign labels.

Table 4.1.1: Marketing Test Done Before Introducing In Market

S.NO	PARTICULARS	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
1	YES	58	63
2	NO	34	37
TOTAL		92	100

Interpretation

Above table shows that, 63 % of the respondents have done marketing test before introducing the product in the market and the remaining 37 % of the respondents have not done marketing test.

Hence it is understood that majority of the respondents have done marketing test before entering in market.

Chart 4.1.1

Table 4.1.2: Channel of Distribution

S.NO	PARTICULARS	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
1	DIRECT SELLING	48	52
2	MIDDLEMEN	37	40
3	OUTSOURCING	7	8
4	OTHERS	0	0
TOTAL		92	100

Interpretation

Above table shows that, 52 % of the respondents have direct selling as their channel of sales, 40% of the respondents have middleman and 8 % of the respondents go for outsourcing.

Hence it is understood that majority of the respondents have direct selling as their channel of sales.

CHART 4.1.2

Table 4.1.3: Dealing With Own Brand

S.NO	PARTICULARS	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
1	YES	9	10
2	NO	83	90
TOTAL		92	100

Interpretation

Above table shows that, 90% of the respondents are not dealing with their own brands / labels and the remaining 10% of the respondents are dealing with their own brands / labels.

Hence it is understood that majority of the respondents are not dealing with their own brands / labels. It is understood that mostly all are dealing with private labels and brands from international market.

Chart 4.1.3

Table 4.1.4: Dealing With Reputed Brands

S.NO	PARTICULARS	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
1	LESS THAN 5 YRS	24	26
2	5-10 YRS	30	33
3	10-15 YRS	26	28
4	MORE THAN 15 YRS	12	13
TOTAL		92	100

Interpretation

Above table shows that, 33 % of the respondents are dealing with reputed brands for 5-10 years, 28% of the respondents are dealing with brands for 10-15 years, 26% of the respondents are dealing with brands for less than 5 years and 13% of the respondents are dealing with brands for more than 15 years.

Hence it is understood that, majority of the respondents are dealing with brands for 5-10 years.

Chart 4.1.4

Table 4.1.5: Have Own Brand in Future

S.NO	PARTICULARS	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
1	YES	60	65
2	NO	32	35
TOTAL		92	100

Interpretation

Above table shows that, 65 % of the respondents are interested to go for their own brand in future and the remaining 35 % of the respondents are not interested to for their own brand.

Hence it is found that, as many respondents are interested to go for their own brands in future, there is going to be high market for Indian brands and more availability of more brands, where the consumers have more choice to decide and purchase.

Chart 4.1.5

Table 4.1.6: Pricing Policy

S.NO	PARTICULARS	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
1	PRICE QUOTED BY BUYER	60	65
2	TENDER/BIDING	28	30
3	ANY OTHER	4	5
TOTAL		92	100

Interpretation

Above table shows that, 65% of the respondents consider price quoted by the buyer as their pricing policy, 30% of the respondents consider tender / biding as their pricing policy and the remaining 5% of the respondents consider other options such as their pricing policy.

Hence it is understood that majority of the respondents consider price quoted by the buyer as their pricing policy.

Chart 4.1.6

Table 4.1.7: Do Competitors Have Advantage Over Firm?

S.NO	PARTICULARS	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
1	YES	32	35
2	NO	60	65
TOTAL		92	100

Interpretation

Above table shows that, 65 % of the respondent’s, doesn’t agree that competitors have advantage over their firm and the remaining 35 % of the respondents, agree that competitors have advantage over their firm.

Hence it is understood that, majority of the respondents have high value products for their international market.

Chart 4.1.7

Table 4.1.8: Competitors Advantage over Firm

S.NO	PARTICULARS	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
1	CHEAP FINANCING, LOW INFRASTRUCTURE COST	5	16
2	BETTER QUALITY OF PRODUCTS	12	38
3	GOOD MARKETING	7	22
4	USE OF BETTER TECHNOLOGY	8	24
TOTAL		32	100

Interpretation

Above table shows that, 38 % of the respondents consider better quality of products as a competitive advantage over their firm, 24% of the respondents opined that, use of better technology, 22 % of the respondents opined that they do good marketing and 16% of the respondents consider cheap financing and low infrastructure as a competitive advantage over their firm.

Hence it is understood that majority of the respondents consider better quality of products as a competitive advantage over their firm.

Chart 4.1.8

Table 4.1.9: Credit Period

S.NO	PARTICULARS	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
1	3 MONTHS	46	50
2	6 MONTHS	18	20
3	PAYABLE WHEN ABLE	2	2
4	NO CREDIT	26	28
TOTAL		92	100

Interpretation

Above table shows that, 50 % of the respondents give a credit period of 3 months for their buyers, 28% of the respondents do not give any credit period for their buyers, 20 % of the respondents give a credit period of 6 months for their buyers and 2% of the respondents allow their buyers to pay when able to pay if they are regular buyers.

Hence, majority of the business with export market are done with credit facility.

Chart 4.1.9

Table 4.1.10: Source of Capital

S.NO	PARTICULARS	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
1	SELF	16	17
2	FAMILY	11	12
3	BANKS	56	61
4	PROFIT	9	10
TOTAL		92	100

Interpretation

Above table shows that, 61 % of the respondents consider banks as their source of capital, 17% of the respondents manage by themselves, 12 % of the respondents consider family as their source of capital and 10% of the respondents consider profit as their source of capital.

Hence it is understood that majority of the respondents consider banks as their source of capital.

Chart 4.1.10

Table 4.1.11: Adopt To Modern Technology

S.NO	PARTICULARS	NO OF RESPODENTS	PERCENTAGE
1	YES	69	75
2	NO	23	25
TOTAL		92	100

Interpretation

Above table shows that 75 % of the respondents shown their interest in going with modern technology and 25 % of the respondents resist to adopt modern technology for their production process.

Hence, majority of the respondents have shown their readiness in adopting modern technology.

Chart 4.1.11

Table 4.1.12: Problems in Adopting With Modern Technology

S.NO	FACTORS	RANK WEIGHTAGE	RANK
1	INADEQUATE FINANCE	208	3
2	BASIC INFRASTRUCTURE AMENITIES	146	4
3	LEGAL PROBLEMS	134	5
4	CAPITAL GOODS	291	1
5	NON AVAILABILITY OF REQUIRED QUALITY INPUTS	275	2

Interpretation

Above table shows that, the respondents have ranked capital goods as the first problem in adopting with modern technology which are followed by non-availability of required quality inputs, inadequate finance, basic infrastructure amenities and legal problems.

Hence it is understood that majority of the respondents have ranked capital goods as one of the major problem in adopting with modern technology.

Chart 4.1.12

Table 4.1.13: Growth in Tirupur

S.NO	PARTICULARS	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
1	FAST & STEADY	58	63
2	STAGNANT	34	37
3	SLOW GROWTH	0	0
4	DOWNTURN	0	0
TOTAL		92	100

Interpretation

Above table shows that, 63 % of the respondents commented that growth level in Tirupur is fast & steady and 37 % of the respondents commented that growth level in Tirupur is stagnant. Hence, it is understood that, the study had been considered at the situation where the growth in Tirupur is considered to be fast and steady in majority of the respondent’s opinion.

Chart 4.1.13

Table 4.1.14: Norms Certified

S.NO	PARTICULARS	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
1	SOCIAL	15	16
2	ENVIRONMENTAL	27	29
3	BOTH	50	55
TOTAL		92	100

Interpretation

Above table shows that 55 % of the respondents have both social and environmental norms certified in their units, 29 % of the respondents have only environmental norms certified in their units and 16 % of the respondents have only social norms certified in their units.

Hence it is understood that majority of the respondents have both social and environmental norms certified in their units.

Chart 4.1.14

Table 4.1.15: Foreign Agent for Promotion of Product

S.NO	PARTICULARS	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
1	YES	70	76
2	NO	22	24
TOTAL		92	100

Interpretation

Above table shows that 76% of the respondents have a foreign agents working for the promotion of their product and 24 % of the respondents do not depend on any foreign agents.

Hence it is understood that majority of the respondents promote their products in international market with agents.

Chart 4.1.15

Table 4.1.16: Tie Ups with Foreign Brands

S.NO	PARTICULARS	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
1	YES	16	17
2	NO	76	83
TOTAL		92	100

Interpretation

Above table shows that 83% of the respondents have not made any tie ups with foreign brands and only 17 % of the respondents have made a tie up with foreign brands. Hence it is understood that majority of the respondents have not made any tie ups with foreign brands.

Chart 4.1.16

Table 4.1.17: Open Office in Foreign Country

S.NO	PARTICULARS	NO OF RESPODENTS	PERCENTAGE
1	YES	63	68
2	NO	29	32
TOTAL		92	100

Interpretation

Above table shows that 68 % of the respondents intend to open an office in foreign country and 32 % of the respondents do not intend to open.

Hence it is understood that majority of the respondents are interested in going for promoting their business by opening new merchandising offices in foreign countries.

Chart 4.1.17

Table 4.1.18: Expansion

S.NO	PARTICULARS	NO OF RESPODENTS	PERCENTAGE
1	SAME LINE	71	77
2	DIVERSIFY	21	23
TOTAL		92	100

Interpretation

Above table shows that 77 % of the respondents prefer to stay in same product line, whereas 23 % of the respondents prefer to diversify their product line. Hence, it is understood from the exporters opinion that, they have good demand for the existing products in the export market.

Chart 4.1.18

5.1.2 Exporters Perspective

Demographic Factors

- 53% of the respondents are concentrating in export market only and are mostly Proprietor.
- 62 % of the respondents are Undergraduates and have business as their family background and hence the majority of the respondents have good experience in business.

Findings Based On Exporters Reasons to Prefer Foreign Labels

- ❖ Majority of the respondents have done marketing test before introducing the product in the market and have direct selling as their channel of sales.
- ❖ Majority of the respondents are not dealing with their own brands. It is understood that mostly all are dealing with private labels and brands from international market and .33 % of the respondents are dealing with reputed brands for 5-10 years.
- ❖ 65 % of the respondents are interested to go for their own brand in future, there is going to be high market for Indian brands and more availability of more brands, where the consumers have more choice to decide and purchase.
- ❖ Majority of the respondents consider price quoted by the buyer as their pricing policy.
- ❖ Majority of the respondent's, doesn't agree that competitors have advantage over their firm and have high value products for their international market and 38 % of the respondents consider better quality of products as a competitive advantage over their firm.

- ❖ 50 % of the respondents give a credit period of 3 months for their buyers. Hence, majority of the business with export market are done with credit facility where majority of the respondents consider banks as their source of capital.
- ❖ 75 % of the respondents shown their interest in adopting modern technology where majority of the respondents have ranked capital goods as one of the major problem in adopting with modern technology.
- ❖ 63 % of the respondents commented that growth level in Tirupur is fast & steady and have both social and environmental norms certified in their units.
- ❖ Majority of the respondents have foreign agents working for the promotion of their product in international market and have not made any tie ups with foreign brands but still interested in going for promoting their business by opening new merchandising offices in foreign countries.
- ❖ 77 % of the respondents prefer to stay in same product line, hence, it is understood from the exporter's opinion that, they have good demand for the existing products in the export market.

5.1.3 Customers Perspective

Demographic Factors

- Majority of the respondents are male and belong to the age group of 18-29 years.
- 56 % of the respondents are married, where Majority of the respondents are employed.

Income & Shopping Factors

- Majority of the respondents are income dependors who shop 6-9 times a year and have shopped at branded outlets and retail stores when there are offers.
- 40.5% of the respondents spend between Rs.5000/- to Rs.10, 000/- once in six months. The same percentage of the respondents also spend more than Rs.10, 000/-.

Purchase Choice of the Customers towards the Apparel Products:

- 46% of the respondents prefer to buy international brands, and believe that, going for international brands brings in status and social acceptance. Hence it is understood that majority of the respondents prefer international brands followed by national brands.
- 52% of the respondents remained neutral and hence, there may be a cluster of respondents who are conscious in deciding the brand in making their purchase decision.
- Majority of the respondents strongly agreed that certain international brands that are manufactured in India are priced high in Indian market compared to the national brands and 33% of the respondents strongly agreed to choose national brands if both the brands are priced at the same level

- The respondents have ranked quality as the first factor followed by brand name, which are further followed by availability of designs, price, value for money, need based and retailer name.

5.1.4 Correspondence Analysis

- ✓ Customers with monthly income between Rs.30000- Rs.50000 prefer to buy national brands. Similarly customers with monthly income between Rs.15000- Rs.30000 are not specific about brands and customers with monthly income of greater than Rs.50000 prefer to go with International brands.
- ✓ Job seekers never buy International brands. Similarly customers who are homemakers and employed buy International brands once in a while, customers who are students buy International brands at times as well as national brands and business people always prefer to buy International brands.
- ✓ Persons who shop less than 3 times a year strongly agree to go with national brands if both are priced same. Similarly persons who shop between 3-6 times a year agree to go with national brands if both are priced same and persons who shop between 6-9 times a year are neutral (i.e. might or might not) go with national brands if both are priced same.

5.2 Discussion & Managerial Implications

The findings of the study leads to the ways for the following discussions and managerial implications to the exporters to utilize the opportunities for the sustainability of their business.

• **Market Strengths & Exporters Opportunities**

Tirupur contributes to 13% of GDP of India. Indian exports are in growing trend and it is expected to rise in steady mode. Rising per capita income, higher disposable incomes, favorable demographics and shift in preference for branded products. Increase in participation of women in workforce and awareness about hygiene & safety by Indian consumers. Changing lifestyles and increasing demand for quality products are set to fuel the need for apparel brands.

Based on the results of the study it is understood that apparel exporters prefer direct selling. They are interested to go for own brands in future. Prefer to adapt to modern technology and interested in tie-up with foreign brands. Indian government has come out with greater opportunities to apparel exporters. “Make in India” projected made provisions for the textile and apparel sector. The Scheme for Integrated Textile Parks provides world-class infrastructure to new textile units.

- ❖ Abundant availability of raw materials such as cotton, wool, silk, jute and manmade fibres.
- ❖ Comparative advantage in terms of skilled manpower and cost of production over major textile producers across globe.
- ❖ Focused and favorable policies instituted by the government will give the industry a fillip.
- ❖ Presence of entire value chain for textile production beginning from production of natural fibre to the production of yarn, fabric and apparel within the country giving edge over countries like Vietnam, Bangladesh etc.
- ❖ Presence of traditional skill sectors i.e. hand loom and handicraft.
- ❖ ❖Market access arrangements with Japan, South Korea, ASEAN, Chile while negotiations with EU, Australia, RCEP countries under process.
- ❖ Readily available market which is poised to grow in future with increased penetration of organized retail, favorable demographics and rising income levels.

Hence, Indian apparel sector has a wider opportunity and exporters should utilize it in a smart way.

Customer’s Expectations

The results of the study reveal that the customers mostly prefer international brands. They are ready to go for national brands if both are priced at same level. They stay with quality and brand name as their first choice. Customers wear branded clothes to look attractive and to impress people, regardless of price they prefer high value for money, prefer fashionable and life style brands, and prefer for the reason for comfort and recognition as it adds value to their personality. In general, customers are influenced by brand name, price offers, design and fashion and quality.

The Indian customer has undergone a remarkable transformation. Just a decade or two ago, the Indian customer saved most of his income, purchased the bare necessities and rarely indulged himself. Today, armed with a higher income, credit cards, exposure to the shopping culture of the west and a desire to improve his standard of living, the Indian consumer is spending like never before. Organized retail with its variety of products and multitude of malls and supermarkets is fuelling their addiction. Most customers' preferences change according to the change in fashion.

Young Shoppers India's population is young, very young. Most consumers have grown up with television, the Internet, and have been exposed to the standards of living and consumer culture abroad. This generation is also making money at a younger age and lots of it, thanks to call centers and other avenues of employment opening up that cater to students in college and schools. As a result they are ready to spend most, if not all of their income on apparel, accessories, and electronics. Apparel Fashion The apparel fashion plays a paramount role in shaping apparel consumerism. As lifestyles change, fashion in India is becoming more diversified, as in the Western countries. Companies and brands that offered monotonous and mundane products for years, have now multiplied their product ranges and new appealing styles, shapes and forms are being launched each season by them.

Managerial Implications

- The Indian government has come up with a number of export promotion policies for the textiles sector. It has also allowed 100 per cent FDI in the Indian textiles sector under the automatic route. **Apparel Exporters in Tirupur should utilize this opportunity to expand their business and to identify new opportunities in the international market.**
- The Department of Handlooms and Textiles, Government of India, has tied up with nine e-commerce players and 70 retailers to increase the reach of handlooms products in the Indian market, which will generate better prices and continuous business, besides facilitating direct access to markets and consumers for weavers. **Every business is digitalized and customers are targeted through e-commerce market also. The exporters may build their own brands and enter the international market through online. Communicating and creating awareness about a brand through online is fast and quick. Hence, it is right time that the apparel manufacturers have to think of creating their own brands for both national and international markets.**
- The Government of India has started promotion of its 'India Handloom' initiative on social media like Facebook, Twitter and Instagram with a view to connect with customers, especially youth, in order to promote high quality handloom products. **Apparel exporters may go in for such campaign in creating awareness about their new brands, which helps them to develop their brands locally, that takes the brands to the international customers globally.**
- The Union Ministry of Textiles, which has set a target of doubling textile exports in 10 years, plans to enter into bilateral agreements with Africa and Australia along with working on a new textile policy to promote value addition, apart from finalizing guidelines for the revised

Textile Up gradation Fund Scheme (TUFS). Under the Market Access Initiative (MAI) Scheme, financial assistance is provided for export promotion activities on focus countries and focus product countries. **Apparel exporters should utilize these opportunities by Indian government, should concentrate in creating brands for the retail sectors. As customers brand choice and spending habits change and are choosy in looking for fashionable brands and Tirupur exporters has fine tune quality products, but fail to brand perfectly. It is suggested to go for their own brand creation, so that they can enjoy the market for the next three decades.**

- **Exporters should make sure to have a market, should make sure to deliver on time. They have to re-examine business and/or product names, create a new brand name and look to the product and understand the international market structure and culture before. Communicate the created name vibrantly so that the brand name sounds better. Understand the pulse of the customers, and hold them tightly and install the brand identity. “Brand in India” or “Brand from India” should be the mantras for apparel products, where the market has huge potential, customers have right expectations and the exporters have good opportunities.....then start.....branding.....!**

CONCLUSION

The main purpose of the study was to understand the perception of the exporters or manufacturers at Tirupur towards branding in their own names while exporting. The results of the study revealed some fruitful conclusions predicting the reasons and why aspects of not branding from Indian labels. Based on the findings, concrete managerial implications are drawn as recommendations, and hence with the approaches of the government of India in promoting “Make in India” aspects, the dream of making Indian brands in global market will sure be achieved in near future.

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